

Towards the Use of Programming without Coding for Navigation Tasks

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Abstract—Learning from Demonstration is a powerful method that allows robots to acquire skills from humans through imitation. There are several strategies in the literature for teaching robots manipulation tasks. However, the aim of this paper is to propose a preliminary study on the possibility of teaching a mobile robot navigation tasks using a single demonstration. To this end, we employed a framework, based on Dynamic Movement Primitives, which has already been proven effective in manipulation tasks. We tried to adapt it to our scenario, taking into account the differences between the two types of tasks. Our approach was validated in a simulated environment with a mobile base equipped with a 2-D laser scan. Preliminary results seem to confirm that it is possible to extend that framework to navigation tasks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Learning from Demonstration (LfD) has become a very popular method to teach robots new tasks in an easy and intuitive way. Indeed, this method does not require any special programming skills, since it is possible to simply show the robot how to perform a task to derive a runtime trajectory planner that allows it to reproduce that same task in different circumstances, without having to write code. Moreover, it makes it easier to adapt robots' capabilities to new and unfamiliar situations, because in such cases the user needs only to provide a new demonstration, rather than having to consider in advance every possible scenario the robot could face and program its behavior accordingly. Overview of LfD different approaches can be found in [1], [2]; however, they all require multiple demonstrations of the same task to learn it, regardless of the design choices. The solution presented in [3], on the other hand, allows to teach tasks to robots using only a single demonstration, proposing an approach closer to programming than to learning. This is a very important aspect, because in this way it becomes easier and easier to deal with robots: this would mean that everyone, even non-expert users, could effectively use them in everyday interactions as well as in situations that may be dangerous or difficult for humans. However, even though their framework is quite general, the authors focus only on manipulation tasks.

In this work, the solution proposed in [3] is used to teach a mobile robot a navigation task. Even though in the literature there are some examples of using the LfD method in applications that include ground vehicles [2], research in this area is still limited. In addition, to the best of the authors'

Figure 1: Simulated environment used to teach a navigation task to a mobile robot. The *start* and *end* point are clearly marked.

knowledge, there is not any application in which they have succeeded in teaching a navigation task relying only on a single demonstration. This is not so trivial and there are a lot of challenges to overcome. This work presents only a preliminary study on the possibility of extending the framework proposed in [3] to mobile bases, as will be discussed further in the next sections.

II. METHOD

The method presented in [3] involves three main processes to transfer skills from humans to robots: teaching, learning and autonomous execution. During the teaching phase, a human operator demonstrates a task to the robot through teleoperation. At the end of the demonstration, the robot processes all the data recorded by the sensors during the demonstration phase and extracts the salient information necessary for learning the task. The result of the learning phase is a program in which all the instructions of the task are encoded. At this point, the robot is able to perform the task autonomously.

In this work, a mobile robot is programmed to execute a navigation task from a *start* point to an *end* point in a simulated environment (Fig. 1). A mobile base can reach any position and orientation in 2-D space, so it needs 3 DOFs to describe its pose; during the teaching process, it is directly controlled by the user through teleoperation (e.g., with a joystick). The only requirement is that the robot is equipped with a 2-D laser scan to capture the point cloud of the environment. As described in [3], each task can be divided into n subtasks, which represent sub-goals for the robot. The teacher can initiate the demonstration with a start signal (e.g., by pressing a button on the joystick or via a GUI). When the demonstration begins, the robot's perception starts recording its pose (2-D position and orientation) and the

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point cloud of the current scene is saved. During the teaching process, the user can explicitly divide a task into subtasks: this can be useful to reduce errors when the robot performs the task autonomously, especially if it moves in a structured environment. The teacher can end a subtask with a signal; when this happens, the perception stops recording and saves all the information (the odometry of the robot and the point cloud of the current scene). If the task is not finished, the recording starts again.

At the end of this process, the learning phase takes place: as mentioned before, the information related to each subtask is elaborated to produce a program that contains all the instructions the robot needs to reproduce the taught task. In particular, we employed a modified version of the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) [4] to encode robot's motion.

After these two phases, the robot is able to autonomously navigate from a starting point to an end point. At the beginning of the task, it determines its current position by acquiring the point cloud of the scene and comparing it to the one stored during the demonstration, using the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm. This process is very important because the robot could start the task from a different point than the one selected during the demonstration: indeed, the DMPs framework allows to generalize the learned trajectory, adapting it to a new starting position. Nevertheless, due to the limitations of the ICP algorithm, the starting point has to be chosen within the initial room and not too far from the original one. Once the robot locates itself, the trajectory is computed considering its current position and the robot follows it until it reaches the goal position, i.e., the point where the user ended the first subtask. Here the robot has to locate itself again, so the process just described is repeated. These operations continue until the robot gets to the *end* point.

III. EXPERIMENTS

We tested this method in a simulated environment running on a DELL G15 equipped with a 10th generation Intel i7 processor and a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 GPU. The simulator we chose is Gazebo 9 interfaced with ROS Melodic. The simulated system used for the experiments is the Summit XL Steel, which has a front and a rear laser scan that are merged to obtain a single one.

During the teaching phase, a user drove the mobile base through the rooms of the building using the keyboard; data from both the odometry of the mobile base and the 2-D laser scans were recorded. The navigation task was divided into 6 subtasks (one for each room); the user ended each subtask before the robot left a room and, at that time, all information was saved. As soon as the demonstration ended, the learning process took place so that the robot could actually learn to perform the navigation task autonomously. At this point, we first decided to verify if the robot had learned the navigation task correctly by selecting as its starting point the same point that we had already chosen during the teaching phase. Since it was able to perfectly reproduce the taught task, we tried to change its initial position and orientation (Fig. 2) to

Figure 2: Robot's initial positions and orientations selected for the experiments.

conduct other experiments and prove that the robot was able to generalize the taught trajectory starting from a different point, as long as it was inside the same room. Again, it was able to correctly perform the navigation task starting from all 4 points shown in Fig. 2.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we applied the framework described in [3] to a mobile robot to teach it a navigation task. The experimental results confirmed that it is possible to extend that framework to this case: the robot was indeed able to perform the taught task starting both from the same point we had chosen during the demonstration and from other points, if they were selected within the initial room. However, there are some aspects that need to be improved: for example, the robot is forced to stop at the end of each subtask to determine its current position, whereas it would be better if the navigation task were executed without interruptions. Furthermore, we did not consider the presence of obstacles: in future work, a strategy to avoid them should be implemented. Nevertheless, this framework can be very promising also for mobile robots, and, at the same time, it can encourage their spreading in different fields, as it allows to program them very quickly and with common devices, such as a joystick.

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